

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series

Vol.XV. Book. I-IV

January-December

2023

Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumar@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

Associate Professor, Dept of English,

Noorul Islam Centre For Higher Education, Kumaracoil,

Thuckalay, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu

jichelnu@gmail.com

Contents

Editors Note	5
A Study on the Separate Legal Identities of the Jains Dr. Anindya Bandyopadhyay	7
Śaivism in the Undivided Balasore District of Odisha Dr. Anil Kumar Acharya	19
Gender Taxonomy in Select Sanskrit Texts Dr. Priya Jose K	28
“The Tragic Fate of Katerina”- A Study Based on Alexander Ostrovsky’s ‘The Thunder Storm’ Dr. Jimly.P	39
Vedic Agriculture and its Implementation in Modern Farming: A Review Garima & Namita Joshi	46
Thematic and Psychological Aspects of the Curses in the light of the Mahābhārata- An Analysis. Pratiksha Goswami	57
Ṣoḍaśāṅgahṛdayam - Essentials of Ayurveda in a nutshell N Pooja, A Arhanth Kumar, K. Vidyalakshmi	73
Humanism in the <i>Bhagavadgītā</i> Dr. K.K. Abdul Majeed	80
Script, Language and Writing Technics of Manuscript Tradition in Kerala Dr. Manju P.M	90
Beyond Silence: Empowering Deaf and Hard of Hearing Students in English Language Learning through Multimodal Approaches Sherin Rahman, Dr R Jinu	96
Veda and the social life of women: A thorough study Dr. Moumita Bhattacharya	107
Ontological Conception of Anekantavada: The Realativistic Interpretation of Jainism Dr. Savithri.A	113
A Representation of Women Subjugation in K.R.Meera’s <i>Hang Woman</i> Meera A S, Dr R Jinu	120
Revisiting Law and Order in the rule of king Mattakala as depicted in Dasakumaracaritam Muthuselvi. A	132
Conservation and Management of Forests in The Hindu Vedas Neetu Joshi, Dr. Namita Joshi	137
Lord Rama as a communicator: Excerpts from Shriramcharitmanas Mayank Bharadwaj	144
Hospitality in the light of Indian culture and Sanskrit Sahitya Dr. Hemant Sharma	161
Exploring the Relationship between Translation and Social Behavior: An Investigation of Bible Translation in Malayalam Dr. Pratheesh Peter	172

Pūrva Mīmāṃsā Vs Śaṅkara's Advaita – A Reading of Śaṅkara's Gītā Upasaṃhāra Bhāṣya	Vishnupriya Srinivasan	177
Does Jaina Epistemology Indicate a Many-Valued Logic	Dr. Sabeena P S	185
जगन्मिथ्यात्वस्य चित्सुखप्रतिपादितं लक्षणम्	डा. सन्तोष .सि.आर्	193
महाभारते सूचिताः जीविकाः – एकमध्ययनम्	डा. के. रतीशः	199
अध्यासस्वरूपविचारः शारीरकमीमांसायां सिद्धान्तबिन्दौ च आशङ्कितविरोधपरिहारश्च	डा. अजिकुमार् पि. वि	203
व्युत्पत्तिवादोक्तदिशा कर्माख्यातार्थविचारः	डा. अजिमोन् सी. एस्	209
शब्दार्थचिह्नविनिर्माणे श्रीहर्षस्य कृतित्वम्	ड. साधन-कुमार-पालः	213
चट्टम्बिस्वामिनः दर्शने वेदान्तयोगदर्शनयोः समन्वयः	डा. आनन्द . एस् , डा. मिधुन्. पि	219
वैशेषिकदर्शने सन्निकर्षविचारः	डा. एस्. शिवकुमारः	225
धर्मशास्त्रदिशा शिक्षायां संस्कृतेः मुख्याङ्गत्वविमर्शः	डा. श्रीजित् टि. जि	230
श्री-अरविन्दस्य अद्वैतवेदान्ततत्त्वानुशीलनम्	डॉ. लक्ष्मीकान्तषडङ्गी	234
सद्योवर्षणम्	डा. ईश्वरः	238
विविधशास्त्रेषु प्रतिपादितस्य गुणतत्त्वस्य पर्यालोचनम्	रिया दत्ता	244
काव्यकारणविमर्शः	डा. कृष्णगोपाल पालः	251
मनुसंहितायां प्रतिफलितं सांख्यतत्त्वम्	लाल्टु रुइदास	257
पुरुषार्थानामुत्सनिरूपणम्	डा. वाणेश्वरजाना	262
आत्मस्वरूपम् – कठोपनिषदि श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतायां च	डा. बिन्दुश्री. के. एस्	269
स्वामिविवेकानन्दस्य जीवनमधिकृत्य प्रणीताधुनिकसंस्कारकृतकाव्यलयेषु सामाजिकमूल्यबोधः	डॉ. सुनीतावर्मन	272
मुख्योपनिषत्सु कर्मविचारः	मौलि एम्	278
रामरायकवेः अद्वैतान्यमतखण्डने जीवेश्वरस्वरूपविमर्शः	विजिता विजयन्. ए	281
वैदिकपरम्परासंरक्षणे श्रीमदनान्दतीर्थभगवत्पादाचार्याणां परमोच्चस्थानत्वम्	डॉ गुरुमध्वाचार्य तिरुमलाचार्य नवली	284
Concept of Ātman in Ayurveda and Tarkaśāstra	Dr. Devan E. M	287
Submission & Subscription		292

Ṣoḍaśāᅅgahᅇdayam - Essentials of Ayurveda in a nutshell

N Pooja¹, A Arhanth Kumar², K. Vidyalakshmi³

Abstract

Acharya Priya Vrat Sharma is a renowned scholar of the 20th century who contributed literatures to the treasure of Ayurveda in the 20th century. Among various works in limelight the book 'Ṣoḍaśāᅅgahᅇdayam' is a hidden treasure. It presents essentials of ayurvedic science in a new perspective of 16 branches against the traditional 8 branch concept. Reading this book gives an insight on need to re-present ayurveda and the basis of mentioning 16 branches in this order. Propagating this work will help the general community, teachers and students to understand, create interest in exploring the science and compose works in Sanskrit.

Keywords: Ṣoḍaśāᅅgahᅇdayam, Essentials, Ayurveda, Acharya Priya Vrat Sharma, 20th Century

Introduction

Books are compiled to express one's view and a tool to gain knowledge on various aspects of a particular subject. In the present era various compiled books are proving to be the source of knowledge for the ayurvedic community. The surge in referring compiled books is either to have easy access to topics included in the curriculum or due to lack of the command over the language in which Ayurveda

1. Final year PG Scholar, Department of P.G. Studies in Ayurveda Samhita and Siddhanta, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Kuthpady, Udupi, Karnataka, 574118 India
2. Associate Professor, Department of P.G. Studies in Ayurveda Samhita and Siddhanta, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Kuthpady, Udupi, Karnataka, 574118 India
3. Head of Department and Professor, Department of P.G. Studies in Ayurveda Samhita and Siddhanta, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Kuthpady, Udupi, Karnataka, 574118 India

is documented thus, review of books to highlight its contributions and area for further scope is essential. Amidst various scholars who are composing texts with an aim to re-present the classics with the need of the hour perspective, Acharya Priya Vrat Sharma has contributed extensively from 20th Century onwards. Ayurveda has always been understood under the purview of *Aṣṭāṅga* (8 branches). But the unique text ‘*Ṣoḍaśāṅgahr̥dayam*’, compiled by P.V. Sharma in Sanskrit puts forth a new dimension of 16 branches.

The author

Acharya Priya Vrat Sharma, well renowned Academician, Physician and Poet of the contemporary era has authored this book. He is the author of various books pertaining to Ayurveda, specially related to Dravyaguṇa. He belongs to the 20th century, born on 1st November 1920, to Shri Pandit Ramavatar Mishra and Shrimati Premdulari devi, near **Śākadvīpa** in Pāṭaliputrā village at Mustaphapur (currently Patna in Bihar).

Title of the book

In the title ‘*Ṣoḍaśāṅgahr̥dayam*’, the terms ‘*Ṣoḍaśa*’ means sixteen, ‘*Āṅga*’ implies part or branch and ‘*Hr̥daya*’ signifies heart/core or essence. This title is apt as this book summarises the whole of Ayurveda under 16 branches thus, the title conveys the authors perspective clearly and also creates an interest in readers to explore the same. This is because *aṣṭāṅga* are the highlight of the Ayurveda according to the classics.

Status of the book

The book *Ṣoḍaśāṅgahr̥dayam* composed by Acharya P.V. Sharma in the form of *padya* (poetry) in Sanskrit is written in Kāśī Gurudhām. He has himself written the Hindi and English translations for the same. 2 editions of the Hindi translation published by Chaukambha Vishwabharati, Varanasi in 1987 are available. Currently its reprint edition of 2016 is available. The English translation titled ‘Essentials of Ayurveda’ is published by Motilal Banarsidass publishers in 1993.

Language and Form of the book

The text is written in Sanskrit language in *padya* form using **Ārya Chandas**. It is divided into 16 chapters titled ‘*Prakaraṇa*’. It summarises all the branches of ayurveda in a nutshell. The Hindi and English translations are also made available by the author for

reaching the masses. The lucid use of poetic phrases and metaphors are seen to express his views.

Content of the book

The author felt an urge to present the science of Ayurveda detailed in various texts, in a nutshell summarising the scope of each branch. It is a compilation of all the concepts related to each branch in a single text. The purpose of composing this text is highlighted as to provide health to entire universe. The title and purpose are linked and justified with similes of lotus and the moon. Just like the fragrance of 16 petal lotus attracts bees, 16 phases of the moon nourish the earth this text will bestow health and keep alive the universal soul.

The book comprises of 16 ‘*Prakaraᅇas*’, each summarising the contents of one branch of Ayurveda thus 16 branches of Ayurveda are explained. The order followed is - *Maulika Siddhāntā*, *Śārīram*, *Dravyaguᅇam*, *Bheᅇaja-kalpanā*, *Rasaśāstram*, *Svasthavᅇttam*, *Rasāyanam*, *Vāᅇikaraᅇam*, *Rogavijᅇānam*, *Kāyacikitsā*, *Mānasaroga*, *Prasūtitantram*, *Kaumārabhᅇtyam*, *Agadatantram*, *Śalyatantram* and *Śālākyatantram*. The index gives the title of each chapter with page numbers, under which the subtopics discussed are also mentioned with sub number and page number. Each branch definition, summary of contents from Bᅇhatᅇrayī and Nighaᅇᅇtu given.

Maulika Siddhāntā mentions 34 elements which includes introduction to Ayurveda and core concepts of Ayurveda. First section highlights the definition of Ayurveda, Ayu, its purpose, need to study the science, branches and qualities of both the student and teacher. Next the summary of concepts like Paᅇcabhūtā, Doᅇa , Dhātu, Malā, Agni, Srotas, order of ᅇaᅇ padārtha , application of **Sāmānya viᅇᅇa**, **6 types of Deᅇa**, 4 subclassification of **Kāla**, **2 types of Bala** and principles related to Vaya and Prakᅇti is briefed.

Śārīram deals with both the anatomy and physiological aspects. Mention of ‘*Paᅇgu andha nyāya*’ explained by **Sāᅇkhyā** Darᅇana to establish the origin of life is told. Definitions of *Śarīra* , *Tvak*, *Kalā*, *Āśaya* are found. Importance of *Asthi*, *Hᅇdaya*, *Mastiᅇka* are highlighted. The description of location of organs like *Yakᅇt*, *Plīha*, *Āntra* and *Vᅇkka* in relation to modern science established. The colour of organs specified, for example - *kapila varᅇa* of *Yakᅇt*. New terminologies coined like ‘*Dehakaᅇkāla*’ for skeleton. The process of

circulation is explained using the term ‘*Cakravaṭ*’.

Dravyaguṇam details qualities of 117 drugs. For further details it is advised to refer his work ‘*Priya Nighantu*’ which is an extensive compendium on drugs. The pillars of Ayurvedic Pharmacology - *Dravya*, *Guṇa*, *Rasa*, *Vīrya*, *Vipāka*, *Prabhāva* are briefed. Various classification of *Dravya* based on *Yoni*, *Prayoga* and *Karma* are described. Mention of *Vāta-pitta-kapha sāmaka gaṇa* is found. Also, he tells to refer 50 *Mahākāṣāya* by Acharya Charaka and 37 *Varga* detailed by *Sūsruta*.

Bheṣaja-kalpanā summarises the *Samgraha vidhi* (Collection), various *Kalpanā* of *Dravya*, *Māna paribhāṣā*, *Auśadha yogāḥ* and their *Mātrā* based on *Kalpanā*, *Vaya*, *Dravya*.

Rasaśāstram - Definition of *Rasa*, *Rasaśāstra*, concept of *Rasaśālā*, groupings like *Dvayam*, *Trika*, *Pañcaka*, *Aṣṭaka*, *Niyāmaka gaṇa*, *Māraka varga*, mention of *Yantra* (5) and *Puṭapāka* (2), brief of *Pārada śodhana*, its *guṇa*, *bheda*, *Māraṇa* of *suvarṇa*, *tutha* and various other minerals, names of *Navaratna*, *Viṣa* and *Upaviṣa*. New term ‘*agnyādhāni*’.

Svasthavṛttam briefs *Dinacaryā*, *Ṛtucaryā*, *Rātricaryā*; features, purpose, benefits of *āhāra*; *Sadvṛttam* (Codes of conduct) in brief, concept of *Janapadoddhvaṃsa* and mention of *svasthalakṣaṇa*.

Rasāyanam includes the features, criteria and benefits of practicing the same. The types are based on *Prayoga* (3) and *Vidhāna* (2). Mention of few important drugs like *Āmalaka*, *Bhallātaka*, *Nāgabala*, *Pippalī*, *Aśvagandhā*; *bhasma* of *Svarṇa*, *Śilājatu* and formulations like *Cyavanaprāśa*, *Medhya rasāyanam* and *Ācāra rasāyanam* are mentioned.

Vājīkaraṇam details the features, purpose and formulations for the purpose. It includes food recipes and medicinal preparations like *Vānarī guṭikā*, *Madanānanda modaka* etc. Important drugs named are *Kapikacchu*, *Bhaṅgā*.

Rogavijñānam includes the purpose of the branch, definition of *Roga*, its two types, the various modes of *Parikṣā* – three, six, eight. The concepts like *Nidāna pañcaka*, *Vikāra ṣaḍ avasthā* and three groups of *sāmānya vikāra* based on *dosha* are mentioned. Further description of 31 diseases is found.

Kāyacikitsā summaries the treatment emphasising on the concept of *Yuktivyapāśraya* for above mentioned 31 diseases.

Mānasaroga includes definition of *Mana* , *Mānasa roga* ; concept of *Anyonyāśraya roga*, mention of diseases like *Mūrcchā*, *Bhrama*, *Unmāda*, *Apasmāra*; conditions like *Pūga mada*, *Dhattūra mada*; treatment including concept of *Anyonya pratidvandva cikitsā* - *kāma*, *śoka*, *krodha*, *bhaya*, *harᅇa*, *īrᅇyā*, *pralobha*, or with formulations like *Caitasa ghr̥ta*, *Kalyāᅇaka ghr̥ta*, *Vacā*, *Paᅇcaᅇavya ghr̥ta*; or with *Sāntvana*, *Tāᅇana*, *Tarjana*, *Vismāpana*, *Cittahanana*. Specific formulation for *Bhrama* - *dhanvayāsa ghr̥ta*, *rasāyana yoga*, *aśvagandha* and *mantha mᅇdvikā* for *mahāvikāra* . Drugs with *Sadyohara* - *Drākᅇā*, *Balā*, *Śatāvari*.

Prasūtitantram summarises the process of conception, growth and development, delivery and treatment for possible medical conditions like *Garbhasrāva* (2), *Garbhaśoᅇa* (1), *Garbhaśūla* (1). Also mentions formulations like *Prajāsthāpana*, *Bᅇᅇhaᅇiᅇya*, *Jivanīya* for *Garbhasthāpana* and for *Garbhadhāraᅇa* mention of *Aśvagandhā cūrᅇa* with *sitā* and *dugdha* or *Aśvagandhā ghr̥ta*. Mentions medication for certain conditions pertaining only to females summarised below.

S.No	Roga	Auᅇadha
1	Yoni roga	Phalasarpi
2	Rakta pradara	Aśoka kᅇirakaᅇāya / Aśokāriᅇᅇa
3	Pradara śūla	Darvyāᅇi kvātha / Puᅇyānuga cūrᅇa
4	Kaᅇᅇārtava associated with śūla	Rajata bhasma + madhu
5	Ārtavarodha	Gᅇhakanyā svarasa / Kumāryāᅇava Rajapravarttanī

Kaumārabhᅇᅇyam decribes *Bāla* as one who is up to 16 years of age. The mention of various *Samᅇkāra* in brief and diseases due to *Bālagraha* are found.

Agadatantram includes its definition, features, classification of *viᅇa* and treatment principle including *prativiᅇā*, *agada*, *dhūpa* and the superior drug *Śirīᅇa*.

Śalyatantram mentions the definition of *Śalya*, classification of *Yantra* (6) and *Śastra* (20), mention of treatment modalities like

Kṣāra, Agnikarma, Raktamokṣaṇa, Nāsāsandhāna, Vraṇopacāra (7), concept of bandhaviśeṣā, vraṇitāgāra, vraṇitacaryā and ātyāyikopacāra based on yukti.

Śālākyaatantram briefs about the formulations for the diseases of eyes, ears, nose, mouth and head as summarised below.

S.No	Roga	Auśadha
1	Netra roga	Triphalā ghr̥ta, Triphalā cūr̥ṇa+ghr̥ta+madhu, Śāstrakarma in dr̥ṣṭi liṅganāśa
2	Kar̥ṇa roga	Apāmarga kṣāra taila, Bilva taila, Svarasa of Laśuna, Ārdraka, Śṛṅgavera
3	Nāsā roga	Sarṣapa taila, Kaṭphala cūr̥ṇa, Vyāghr̥i taila, Śaḍbindu taila
4	Mukha roga, Śiroroga	Triphalā ghr̥ta, Kaṭphala nasya, Saptāmṛtaloha

Unique features

Unlike classical texts of Ayurveda which describe the Aṣṭāṅga of Ayurveda, here 16 branches have been detailed. The author would have had a basis to mention the branches in the following order. As he highlights the purpose of writing the book to be maintenance of health, first branches dealing with prevention and maintenance is described first followed by those branches dealing with cure of diseases.

Definitions of Aṣṭāṅga are found in Susrutha Samhita. Here the definition of other branches has also been given. This book is more from the purview of practical application. Based on this the subtypes and new terminologies have been introduced like - Dehakaṅkāla, Agnyādhānī etc. The classification of Deśa is for understanding the doṣha dominance which is relevant to maintain health and treat diseases as highlighted in table. The number of types in various contexts varies from that mentioned in classical texts. Detail description of drugs available in the present era is emphasised. Methods of preparation of various kalpanās is briefed. Formulations relevant in that time period based on drug availability are highlighted. Among the 31 diseases briefed along with concise

treatment protocol, conditions like śula, śītapitta, galaganda, kamala, ślīpada are mentioned independently.

S.No	Desha	Dosha Dominance
1	<i>Jāᅇgala</i>	<i>Vāta</i>
2	<i>Saindhava sāmudra</i>	<i>Kapha pitta</i>
3	<i>Saikata</i>	<i>Vāta pitta</i>
4	<i>Pārvatya</i>	<i>Vāta kapha</i>
5	<i>Ānūpa</i>	<i>Kapha</i>
6	<i>Madhya</i>	<i>Sādhāraᅇa</i>

Conclusion

Such books are examples of target-based approach which provide solutions to the problems prevalent in that era. The branches highlighted and rearranged based on the education curriculum established during that period. The basis of this compilation is both academic and clinical. It also emphasises on the need to update and revise the presentation of classical texts to generate interest, enthusiasm among Ayurveda community and humanity at large to explore and adopt this science. 4

Works Cited

- Śarmā, P.V. “Ṣoḁaśāᅇgahᅇᄁayam”. Reprint ed., Chaukhambha Visvabharati, Varanasi, 2016.
- Rādhākāntadeva. “Śabdakalpadrumah”, Reprint ed., Nag Publishers, Delhi, 2006.

4 Note: No Financial support and sponsorship , Consent is obtained from the publishers – Chaukhambha Visvabharati, Varanasi. and There are no conflicts of interest